

The Influence of e-WOM, Trust, Content Marketing and Brand Image on Purchase Decisions on Tiktok (Case Study on Skincare Product Sales)

Rizki Galura Septiana
Universitas Mercu Buana Jakarta, Indonesia

Mirza
Universitas Mercu Buana Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:- The objective of this research is to examine how e-commerce, trust, content marketing, and brand image on the purchase decision of skincare products on TikTok. The study population consists of TikTok users living in Jakarta who have experience purchasing skincare products on TikTok, with a sample size of 100 individuals. The data analysis method employed is structural equation modeling - partial least squares (SEM-PLS). The study's results reveal that e-commerce and content marketing exert a positive and statistically significant influence on purchase decisions. Conversely, trust and brand image demonstrate a positive impact, although not statistically significant regarding purchase decisions.

Keywords:- Purchase Decision, E-WOM, Trust, Content Marketing, Brand Image.

I. INTRODUCTION

With technological advances continuing to develop rapidly, humans are increasingly finding convenience in various aspects of life. One of the most significant technological developments that has experienced change in the last few decades is communication and information technology. This change was termed "Revolution" by Wriston (Maesurah, 2020), because it was able to have a very rapid impact on human life. In particular, Wriston states that this information revolution has the potential to influence global power structures, which are based on rapid development and the wide dissemination of knowledge and information in various fields.

Shopping activity is an element of human life that is carried out to fulfill needs for goods and services. Shopping online is now a practice that can be done flexibly, anytime and anywhere, thanks to the ease of carrying out transactions. This can then be explained through consumer behavior, which are actions and activities carried out by individuals, groups, and organizations related to selecting, purchasing, and using goods or services to meet needs and desires (Kotler & Keller, 2016).

Analysis and selection activities are carried out before deciding on a location or alternative media in which someone wants to make a shopping choice. Consumers choose media or places to shop based on the needs they are looking for. (Wulandari, 2013). Several years ago, the existence of applications could be classified based on their function, including applications for social media and applications for shopping, but as time goes by, online social media applications

that are now used by people around the world, such as Tiktok, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and others, are being utilized. by business people to market their products.

Tiktok is an application product from a company called Bytedance which is based in China, which is an online social media platform with the main feature of providing a place for its users to express their creativity through short videos lasting 30 seconds to three minutes. Another feature of Tiktok is the Live feature where content creators can interact directly with their audience. The development of the Tiktok application as an online social media has provided entertainment and education for users. The increasing number of Tiktok users shows that there is an opportunity for virality for anyone who uses it. Viral is the achievement of a high number of impressions for content on social media in a short time, which appears as a result of sharing activities with other users and the content's ability to reach many users on social media. (Tellis, MacInnis, Tirunillai, & Zhang, 2019).

So to date, Tiktok, which originally was a social media, has expanded its function, namely as an online promotional application which is supported by the increasingly diverse features provided by Tiktok which support the realization of persuasive communication.

Through persuasive communication, viewers can search for and get to know products, get the information they need, and compare both the products and services offered, to make a decision to choose Tiktok as a place to shop. The consumer decision making process is an activity carried out in several stages and does not occur only at one particular time. This process generally starts with needs analysis, continues with information search, alternative evaluation, and finally decision making.

The increasing diversity of marketing content in various forms, supported by quality products and proven benefits directly by affiliates or other users who have tried the product, is able to make users satisfied and willing to engage in online mutual exchange (e-WOM), namely by spreading the news about this product widely through the "share" feature and providing testimonials for other users through the "comment" feature in the Tiktok application.

Tiktok emphasizes various regulations that must be fulfilled by content creators in promoting their products. Therefore, the content creator's ability to promote products needs to be a priority when promoting on Tiktok. Content

marketing is a marketing technique used to create and disseminate high-quality, useful and interesting content to reach a clear and understandable target audience with the aim of encouraging profitable customer behavior (Ari Nugroho & Zaki Mahendra, 2021). With content marketing, it is considered capable of building close relationships with the audience, making it easier for sellers to achieve goals in marketing communications activities, namely achieving purchases from consumers.

By realizing good content marketing and effective e-WOM, it will increase the trust of Tiktok users, both in the products offered and trust in Tiktok as an application that is able to facilitate buying and selling. The existence of user trust in Tiktok, such as providing products in accordance with those marketed by the seller, fast product handling from the time the user chooses the product to paying the bill, good product packaging and fast and accurate product delivery becomes a mediator for content marketing and e-commerce. -WOM. The combination of these three variables can influence the behavior of Tiktok users, who initially only become viewers, then become consumers through the user's purchase decision process.

Apart from these three variables, Tiktok must also consider brand image which is able to provide other views from consumers apart from just the functional side. A brand is a company's most valuable asset and is one of the differentiating factors among similar companies to be taken into consideration by consumers, so that if Tiktok has an image that is attached to it, consumers will maintain their loyalty when shopping online on Tiktok.

The rapid development of skincare sales on Tiktok shows that there is a purchasing decision process from consumers which is influenced by various aspects. In this research, the author wants to analyze the influences that can influence customers to choose Tiktok and decide to make purchases on Tiktok, which focuses on the influence of e-WOM because of the freedom for users and sellers on Tiktok to interact with other users, so that it will give rise to user trust in TikTok. Then on content marketing, because Tiktok is an application that facilitates and gives users freedom to create creative content, on Tiktok. This will improve Tiktok's brand image which is related to the shift in Tiktok's function as a social media to an online buying and selling media, so that in the end it will encourage users to make purchasing decisions on Tiktok.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Consumer behavior is the actions and activities carried out by individuals, groups and organizations related to selecting, purchasing and using goods or services to fulfill needs and desires (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Consumer behavior is the actions directly involved in the acquisition, consumption and consumption of products or services, including the processes that precede and follow these actions (Sangadji & Sopiah, 2013).

Social influence describes the influence a person gets from someone other than themselves, which will strengthen

their decision to choose something based on their preferences and beliefs.

This theory refers to the work of Kelman (1981) and Kapitan & Silvera (2016) where the understanding of the influence of social media influencers on their followers lies in thought and emotional processes (Kapitan & Silvera, 2016; Kelman, 2006).

Social influence acts as a balance between one's own personal interests and the interests of others. Social influences can also play an important role in encouraging responsible consumption and production habits among individuals. For example, when someone sees their peers engaging in responsible consumption and production practices, they are more likely to do the same. (Shah & Asghar, 2023)

According to Hanaysha (2018), purchase decision is behavior that involves a series of choices made by consumers before making a purchase, which begins when consumers have a choice to fulfill their needs. Initially, consumers will carry out problem recognition which aims to satisfy their needs and desires. Then consumers will start looking for information (seek information) from internal sources (usually from past experiences) about the product or external sources such as friends, family, neighbors, social media or product packaging labels. Then in the end consumers will evaluate alternative options and choose the brand that is most suitable and satisfies their needs (Hanaysha, 2018).

Viral marketing or also known as electronic word of mouth (e-WOM) is marketing that uses the internet to create a word of mouth effect in supporting the business and objectives of the marketing itself (Kotler & Keller, 2016).

Trust in marketing is defined as loyalty, advocacy and great involvement from customers (Rahman, 2017). Consumer trust is also defined as all the knowledge that consumers have and all the conclusions made by consumers about objects, attributes and benefits, which if continued to increase will produce very loyal consumers (Pyle et al., 2021).

According to Kotler Keller (2016) trust is a company's willingness to rely on its business partners, which depends on a number of interpersonal and interorganizational factors, such as partner competence, integrity, honesty and sincerity (Kotler & Keller, 2016).

Content marketing is a marketing strategy carried out by creating and producing content with the aim of providing information about a product to a target audience that is persuasive. This approach to marketing strategy usually focuses on creating content that is valuable, relevant, and also done consistently in order to attract attention, retain the audience, and also to generate the desired profits.

Pulizzi defines content marketing as a marketing process for creating and distributing interesting content to audiences or consumers to increase consumer awareness, invite and encourage potential consumers to take actions that are profitable for the company (Pulizzi, 2015).

Brand image is a positive impression of a product brand that a company instills in the minds of consumers. Consumers measure brands by considering choosing or assessing the brand image of a product with a positive impression in its field, such as product reputation and product excellence and easy recognition.

According to Utari (2023), Brand image is a concept that refers to an attitude of trust and preference towards a brand, so that it can encourage consumers to shop when they have a positive perception of the brand image. Utari (2023) stated that there is a significant influence between brand image on consumer shopping interest, which means that the stronger the brand image, the greater consumer interest in shopping (Utari et al., 2023).

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a quantitative approach to evaluate the influence of e-commerce, trust, content marketing and brand image on purchase decisions. Data was collected by distributing questionnaires to 100 respondents after testing the validity and reliability of the research instrument, which stated that all items on the instrument were valid and reliable. Next, the data was analyzed descriptively for each variable, and inferential analysis was carried out using SEM-PLS to test the relationship between endogenous and exogenous variables. Apart from that, hypothesis testing is carried out quantitatively with the aim of testing the truth of the hypothesis that has been proposed (Arikunto, 2019).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive research results show that the e-WOM variable is included in the medium category and tends to be high as seen from the percentage of 79% which shows that out of 100 respondents, 79% of respondents put e-WOM in the medium category and 21% which shows 21 respondents out of 100 respondents put e-WOM is at high and very high.

Meanwhile, the trust variable is in the low category, tends to be medium, which can be seen from the percentage of 49%, which shows that out of 100 respondents, 49% of respondents put trust in the low category and 34%, which shows 34 respondents out of 100 respondents, put trust in the medium category.

Then for the content marketing variable it is in the high category which can be seen from the percentage of 77% which shows that out of 100 respondents, 77% of respondents put content marketing in the high category and 7% which shows 7 respondents out of 100 respondents put content marketing in the very high category and 16%, indicating 16 respondents out of 100 respondents, stated that content marketing was in the medium category.

Brand image variable it is in the medium category which can be seen from the percentage of 90% which shows that out of 100 respondents, 90 respondents put the brand image in the medium category and 10% which shows 10 respondents out of 100 respondents put the brand image in the very high category.

The results also show that the purchase decision variable is in the high category which can be seen from the percentage of 50% which shows that out of 100 respondents, 50 respondents placed the purchase decision in the high category, 24% showed the purchase decision was in the medium category, 19% showed the purchase decision was in the low category and 7%, which shows that 7 respondents out of 100 respondents placed Purchase Decision in the very high category.

The analysis applied in this research is Path Analysis using SmartPLS 3.2.9 software. The PLS method was chosen because it does not require a large sample and focuses on prediction purposes. With the PLS approach, it is assumed that all variance dimensions have relevance to explain (Ghozali, 2021). The data analysis process using SmartPLS software consists of two stages, namely the Measurement Model and the Structural Model.

The research validity test was obtained through several stages, namely Convergent Validity in the form of Outer Loadings (Loading Factors) and Average Variance Extranced (AVE) as well as Discriminant Validity in the form of Fornell-Larker Criterion and Cross Loading. In the Convergent Validity test results, there are several Outer Loadings and AVE values that do not meet the standard above 0.5. The initial AVE value is as follows.

Table 1. AVE Value in Research

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
<i>Purchase decision (Y)</i>	0.463
<i>e-WOM (X1)</i>	0.503
<i>Trust (X2)</i>	0.544
<i>Content marketing (X3)</i>	0.469
<i>Brand image (X4)</i>	0.603

Based on this table, it can be seen that the AVE (*Average Variance Extracted*) value for the e-WOM variable does not meet the desired standard, namely 0.5. Therefore, researchers need to delete several *Outer Loading* Variables whose values are below the standard of 0.5. The reflection indicator is categorized as high if the correlation exceeds 0.7; However, because this research is in the initial stage, the standard used is 0.5-0.6 (Ghozali, 2021).

The author carried out one elimination step to increase the validity and reliability of the research by eliminating the lowest indicator of each variable. The indicators removed include Y4 with an *Outer Loading* value (0.523), X37 with an *Outer Loading* value (0.568), and X310 with an *Outer Loading* value (0.565). After this deletion, the calculation results show the AVE value for Discriminant Validity as follows.

Table 2. Second Processing AVE Value

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
<i>Purchase decision (Y)</i>	0.517
<i>e-WOM (X1)</i>	0.503
<i>Trust (X2)</i>	0.544
<i>Content marketing (X3)</i>	0.518
<i>Brand image (X4)</i>	0.602

Based on this table, it can be seen that all variables have met the established AVE criteria, namely having a value greater than 0.5. These results indicate that the Convergent Validity test is acceptable, and the next step is to carry out the *Discriminant Validity test* via *Fornell-Larker Criterion* and *Cross Loading*.

Fornell-Larker Criterion test is carried out by comparing the value of $\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$ (Square Root of *Average Variance Extracted*) with other latent variables. The concept that must be fulfilled is that the correlation value $\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$ with the variable construct itself must be greater than the correlation with other variable constructs. Fulfillment of this concept can be seen through the diagonal and vertical directions in each variable column.

The next step to test *Discriminant Validity* is to use the *Cross Loading test*, which is a test of the *Outer Loading value* of a variable construct which should have a higher value for its own variable compared to other variables. Based on these results, it can be concluded that the *Cross Loading value* of each indicator on the variable is higher than its relationship with other variable constructs.

the *Fornell-Larker Criterion* and *Cross Loading* calculations show that the validity of the research, which refers to *Discriminant Validity*, shows the level of validity.

The next test is to test the reliability of the research through *Composite Reliability* and *Cronbach's Alpha values* which exceed 0.6. The following is the research reliability value.

Table 3 Cronbach's Alpha Processing Values

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Standard d Cronbach's Alpha
Purchase decision (Y)	0.760	0.7
e-WOM (X1)	0.858	0.7
Trust (X2)	0.880	0.7
Content marketing (X3)	0.866	0.7
Brand image (X4)	0.906	0.7

Table 4 Composite Reliability Processing Values

Variable	Composite Reliability	Standard d Composite Reliability
Purchase decision (Y)	0.840	0.6
e-WOM (X1)	0.889	0.6
Trust (X2)	0.904	0.6
Content marketing (X3)	0.895	0.6
Brand image (X4)	0.923	0.6

Based on this table, the *Cronbach's Alpha value* shows a value that exceeds the standard, namely 0.7, so it can be concluded that all variables meet the reliability criteria. Apart

from that, the *Composite Reliability value* also exceeds the standard of 0.6 and is even higher than the *Cronbach's Alpha value*. This shows that all research variables meet the appropriate reliability requirements to be the basis for SEM analysis using SmartPLS.

The results of measuring validity and reliability using the Measurement Model above confirm that the data collection instruments used in this research are valid and reliable. These findings indicate that the research measuring instruments have reliable consistency

➤ *Structural Model Analysis*

Structural model or *inner model analysis* was carried out with the aim of predicting the relationship between latent variables (Ghozali, 2021). Evaluation of the inner model can be seen through several indicators, including the coefficient of determination (R^2), *model fit test*, and path coefficient.

The first step is to analyze the coefficient of determination. There are three categories in grouping the R^2 value: if the R^2 value is more than 0.75, then it is in the strong category; if the R^2 value is between 0.5 – 0.75, then it is in the moderate category; and if the R^2 value is between 0.25 – 0.5, then it is in the weak category (Hair et al., 2021). The following are the results of the R^2 value test in the final *Outer Model testing*.

Table 5. Determination Coefficient Values

Variable	R-Square	Category
Purchase decisions	0.684	Moderate

Based on the data in the table, it can be concluded that the *Purchase decision variable* has an R-Square value of 0.684 after being calculated using SmartPLS. This means that around 68.4% of the variance in *Purchase decisions* can be explained by the e-WOM, *Trust*, *Content marketing* and *Brand image variables*, while the remaining 31.6% is influenced by other factors outside the variables listed in the model.

Next, testing was carried out to determine the Goodness of Fit (GoF) value with the aim of evaluating the level of suitability and feasibility of the research model. In GoF assessment, there are three criteria that can be used to conclude the results. If the value is in the range 0 – 0.25, then the feasibility level is considered small (GoF Small). If the value is in the range 0.25 – 0.36, then the feasibility level is considered medium (GoF Medium). If the value exceeds 0.36, then the feasibility level is considered large (GoF Large). The following are the GoF values in the context of this research.

Table 6. Research GoF Value

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	R^2
e-WOM (X1)	0.602	0.648
Trust (X2)	0.518	
Content marketing (X3)	0.503	
Brand image (X4)	0.517	

Purchase decision (Y)	0.543	
Average	0.537	0.648

Based on this table, it is known that the average AVE value is 0.537 and R² is 0.648, so the GoF value can be calculated as follows:

$$GoF = \sqrt{AVE \times R^2}$$

$$GoF = \sqrt{0,537 \times 0,648}$$

$$GoF = 0,606$$

From the results of these calculations, it can be concluded that the Goodness of Fit (GoF) value in this study reached 0.606. This indicates that the overall performance of the prediction model, which is evaluated from the agreement between the inner model and the outer model, has a large level of feasibility. This assessment is based on the criterion that a GoF value exceeding 0.36 is considered a large level of feasibility.

➤ Hypothesis testing

Table 7. Path Coefficient Value

Variable	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values	Information
X1 □□Y	0.606	0.606	0.097	6,222	0,000	Accepted
X2 □□Y	0.020	0.024	0.128	0.153	0.878	Rejected
X3 □□Y	0.275	0.271	0.136	2,017	0.044	Accepted
X4 □□Y	0.041	0.030	0.090	0.459	0.646	Rejected

Based on this table, it can be interpreted that:

- The parameter coefficient for the variable X1 on Y is 0.606, indicating a positive influence of X1 on Y. It can be interpreted that the higher the value of X1, the value of Y will also increase. A one unit increase in X1 will increase the Y value by 60.6%. The results of the bootstrap test show that the estimated coefficient of The P value is 0.013 < 0.05, so H1 is accepted, indicating that the influence of e-WOM on purchase decisions is significant
- The parameter coefficient for the variable X2 on Y is 0.020, indicating that there is a positive influence of A one unit increase in X2 will increase the Y value by 2%. The results of the bootstrap test show that the estimated coefficient of The P value is 0.878 > 0.05, so H2 is rejected, indicating that there is no significant influence of trust on purchase decisions.
- The parameter coefficient for the variable X3 on Y is 0.275, indicating that there is a positive influence of A one unit increase in X3 will increase the Y value by 27.5%. The results of the bootstrap test show that the estimated coefficient of The P value is 0.044 < 0.05, so H3 is accepted, indicating that the influence of content marketing on purchase decisions is significant.
- The parameter coefficient for the variable X4 on Y is 0.041, indicating that there is a positive influence of X4 on Y. It can be interpreted that the higher the value of A one

The next step involves testing the hypothesis using a t-test to assess the significance of the structural path coefficient parameters. The significance of the influence between latent variables can be observed from the statistical significance value, while the significance of the parameter coefficients is calculated using the *bootstrapping method*. *Bootstrapping* is a non-parametric procedure used to test whether coefficients such as outlying weights, outlying loadings, and path coefficients are significant by estimating the standard errors for their estimates. The bootstrapping test also aims to determine the direction of the relationship and the significance of the relationship for each latent variable.

To measure the significance of the path, the critical value of the Path Coefficient is used which is indicated by the t value. In the hypothesis with a two-way test at a significance level of 5%, the critical t value is 1.98. If the t-value is greater than 1.98, it can be considered that there is an influence between the variables. Next, a significance test is carried out by comparing the P value with a significance level of 0.05. If the P value is smaller than 0.05, it can be concluded that there is a significant effect. The following are the output results from the *bootstrapping test* in this research.

unit increase in X4 will increase the Y value by 4.1%. The results of the bootstrap test show that the estimated coefficient of The P- value is 0.646 > 0.05, so H4 is rejected, indicating that there is no significant influence of brand image on purchase decisions .

Fig 1. Bootstrapping output

Thus it can be concluded that of the 4 hypotheses proposed, there are two hypotheses that are rejected, namely H2 and H4 which state that trust and brand image have no influence on

purchase decisions, while the other hypotheses are accepted, namely H1 and H3 which state that e-WOM, and content marketing has an influence on purchase decisions.

V. CONCLUSION

- e-WOM has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions with the highest indicator being the intensity indicator relating to the need for skincare and the lowest indicator being positive opinions relating to purchasing skincare on Tiktok which is cheaper compared to other marketplaces.
- Trust has a positive but not significant effect on purchase decisions with the highest indicator being the reliability indicator which is related to Tiktok's reliability in securing transactions and the lowest indicator is also the reliability indicator which is related to Tiktok's reliability in resolving problems if there is a discrepancy in orders.
- Content marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions with the highest indicator, namely the persuasion indicator which is related to the seller's ability to offer skincare products on Tiktok using polite language and the lowest indicator is also the Persuasion indicator which is related to the seller being able to persuade consumers to buy skincare on Tiktok with good promotions.
- Brand image has a positive but not significant effect on purchase decisions with the highest indicator being the tenacity indicator which is related to Tiktok's ability to maintain service quality both as social media and online shopping media and the lowest indicator is connotation relating to Tiktok being known as a popular online shopping place. Facilitate consumers to see products being sold in real time.

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